

VARIABLE STIFFNESS COMPOSITE LAMINATES FOR DOUBLY CURVED PLATES USING LAMINATION PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

A methodology is presented for the optimisation of variable stiffness composite laminates for complex doubly curved geometries. As an example, this is here applied to a pre-twisted plate subjected to combined centrifugal and pressure loading. Lamination parameters are used to reduce the complexity of composite laminate design to a convex and continuous design space using a reduced number of variables. Lamination parameters are varied over the geometry using spline surface interpolation over a grid of control points and the optimal values found using a gradient based optimiser. A method for restricting the variation of lamination parameters over the geometry in relation to minimum turning radii of automated fibre placement heads and the distance between lamination parameter control points is discussed and demonstrated. A *MATLAB* script was developed to define variable angle tow paths over a doubly curved geometry. The tow paths for every ply were found using a two-stage optimisation routine. A genetic algorithm was firstly used to design the variable tow paths of each ply, this was then used as an initial design for a gradient based optimiser to further improve the tow paths of the laminate. The variable angle tow laminate designed showed good agreement to the optimal stiffness found through optimisation of the lamination parameter distribution.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials such as carbon fibre reinforced plastics has increased rapidly in recent years due to their superior strength and stiffness to weight ratio. Designing a composite laminate consists of selecting the best arrangement of the constituent materials. Traditionally, this involves finding the best combination of several straight-fibre layers to create a unidirectional (UD) laminate of constant stiffness (CS) with the best mechanical properties for its application [1]. As the loading magnitude and direction varies throughout most engineering structures, so too should the fibre direction. Therefore, it would be beneficial to alter the stiffness of the composite laminate throughout the structure by creating a variable stiffness (VS) laminate. VS laminates can be created in a manner of different ways [2]. Conventionally, a VS laminate can be created using piece-wise discontinuation and/or addition of patches of UD plies [3] but this creates discontinuous loads paths throughout the fibres of the plies. A more efficient use of composite laminates is to steer the fibres over the structure using variable angle tow (VAT) composites. VAT laminates are created using an automated fibre placement (AFP) machine to steer the fibres over the structure. The use of VAT composite has recently received considerable interest in the structural design of wind turbines [4], aeroplane wings [5,6] and fuselage panels [7] to name a few. The structural optimisation of laminated composites can become complex, especially if the stiffness is directly derived from a stacking sequence with a large number of plies, leading to a large

number of design variables needed to define a laminate. The complexity and number of design variables can be significantly reduced by using lamination parameters.

In the following section the objectives are set out, following that lamination parameters are introduced as a means of reducing the complexity and number of variables needed to define a composite laminates stiffness. A method is then discussed in the following section to vary lamination parameters over a surface to create a variable stiffness laminate. The optimal lamination parameters distribution to reduce displacement for a pre-twisted plate geometry under centrifugal and pressure loading is then found. A method is then discussed in which to constrain the variation of lamination parameters in relation to typical automated fibre placement manufacturing constraints, with the difference this makes to the optimal distribution discussed. Finally, a method is demonstrated that is able to extract VAT ply definitions and stacking sequence to define a variable stiffness laminate that closely matches the optimal lamination parameter distribution.

2. OBJECTIVES

The aim of this investigation is to develop an optimisation methodology for the stiffness tailoring of variable stiffness laminates for doubly curved plates. As an example, this is applied to the stiffness optimisation of a pre-twisted plate subjected to combined centrifugal and pressure loading to minimise the displacement of a plate. The pre-twisted plate had a span and width of 1000mm and 500mm respectively, with a linear twist rate along the span, with a final tip twist of 70°. The laminate had a uniform thickness of 12mm and was rotating about an axis located away from the root in the negative y direction. Typical material properties for a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy lamina of thickness 0.125mm were used and shown in table 1. A *MATLAB* script was used to determine the individual element shell stiffness which were then imported into Abaqus finite element software to determine the displacements of the plate. The centrifugal loading was automatically calculated by Abaqus. The plate also had a pressure loading acting to the normal of the underneath (i.e. positive z direction) of the plate. The optimiser used the sum of the magnitude of the displacement of all nodes in the pre-twisted plate as the objective function.

$$\text{Minimise} \quad f = \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\Delta x_i^2 + \Delta y_i^2 + \Delta z_i^2} \quad (1)$$

where i and N are the node number and total number of nodes respectively.

Engineering Constant	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	ν_{12}	ρ (kg/m ³)
Value	140	10	5	0.3	1600

Table 1: Typical material properties for a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy lamina.

3. LAMINATION PARAMETERS

Lamination parameters (LP), first introduced by Tsai and Hahn [8], provide a compact notation for the description of the stiffness of any laminate lay-up configuration. The complete set of stiffness matrices for any laminate can be described as linear function of terms of only 12 lamination parameters $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^A$, $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^B$ and $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^D$. When LP are used as design variable for stacking sequence definition, the number of variables is independent of the number of layers and have values $-1 \leq \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^{[A,B,D]} \leq 1$, thus reducing the complexity of the optimisation problem. The ABD stiffness matrix of a composite laminate can be represented in terms of lamination parameters using

$$\begin{aligned}
 \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} \\ A_{22} \\ A_{12} \\ A_{66} \\ A_{16} \\ A_{26} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_1^A & \xi_2^A & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_1^A & \xi_2^A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^A & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^A & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \xi_3^A/2 & \xi_4^A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_3^A/2 & -\xi_4^A & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{bmatrix} & \quad \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} \\ B_{22} \\ B_{12} \\ B_{66} \\ B_{16} \\ B_{26} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{h^2}{4} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \xi_1^B & \xi_2^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\xi_1^B & \xi_2^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_3^B/2 & \xi_4^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_3^B/2 & -\xi_4^B & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{bmatrix} \\
 \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} \\ D_{22} \\ D_{12} \\ D_{66} \\ D_{16} \\ D_{26} \end{bmatrix} &= \frac{h^3}{12} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_1^D & \xi_2^D & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_1^D & \xi_2^D & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^D & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^D & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \xi_3^D/2 & \xi_4^D & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_3^D/2 & -\xi_4^D & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where the lamination parameters are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^A &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta(z), \cos 4\theta(z), \sin 2\theta(z), \sin 4\theta(z)] dz, \\
 \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^B &= \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta(z), \cos 4\theta(z), \sin 2\theta(z), \sin 4\theta(z)] z dz, \\
 \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^D &= \frac{3}{2} \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta(z), \cos 4\theta(z), \sin 2\theta(z), \sin 4\theta(z)] z^2 dz
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

and $\theta(z)$ is the distribution function of the ply orientation through the normalised thickness coordinate $\bar{z} = (2/h)z$ of a laminate of thickness h . The material invariants are defined using the reduced stiffnesses Q_{ij} for a UD lamina as

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_1 &= [3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}]/8, \\
 U_2 &= [Q_{11} - Q_{12}]/2, \\
 U_3 &= [Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}]/8, \\
 U_4 &= [Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}]/8, \\
 U_5 &= [Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}]/8
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

From equation 2, it is evident only four LP ($\xi_1^A, \xi_2^A, \xi_1^D$ and ξ_2^D) are needed to define any laminate with a balanced and symmetric stacking sequence. Furthermore, only two LP (ξ_1^A and ξ_2^A) are needed if the laminate is homogenised as $\xi_1^A = \xi_1^D$ and $\xi_2^A = \xi_2^D$. Relationships between LP need to be provided to ensure the combination is feasible. The feasible region for the in-plane and out-of-plane stiffness are defined using

$$2(\xi_1^j)^2 - \xi_2^j - 1 \leq 0 \tag{5}$$

where $j = [A, D]$. According to Wu et al [9], the following is all that is required to accurately bound the feasible region of the four LP for a balanced and symmetric laminate

$$\begin{aligned}
 5(\xi_1^A - \xi_1^D)^2 - 2(1 + \xi_2^A - 2(\xi_1^A)^2) &\leq 0, \\
 (\xi_2^A - 4t\xi_1^A + 1 + 2t^2)^3 - 4(1 + 2|t| + t^2)^2(\xi_2^D - 4t\xi_1^D + 1 + 2t^2) &\leq 0 \\
 (4t\xi_1^A - \xi_2^A + 1 + 4|t|)^3 - 4(1 + 2|t| + t^2)^2(4t\xi_1^D - \xi_2^D + 1 + 4|t|) &\leq 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $t = [-1, -0.75, -0.5, -0.25, 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1]$ (or, for better accuracy $t = [-1, -0.8, -0.6, -0.4, -0.2, 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1]$). In this paper, only homogenised laminates are used and therefore, only ξ_1^A , ξ_2^A and equation 5 are needed to define the laminates. Inclusion of all LP can be used in conjunction with this method. Stacking sequence optimisation using LP requires a minimum two-step process [10]. Firstly, the optimal LP values are found using gradient based optimisers. Secondly, the stacking sequence with the closest LP to the optimal is then found, usually through a metaheuristic optimiser, such as a GA, because the design space is highly non-convex.

4. LAMINATION PARAMETER VARIATION OVER STRUCTURE

Wu et al [9] used B-spline surface interpolation between control points to vary LP over a rectangular plate. This allowed for a smooth and continuous distribution and interpolation of lamination parameter values in positions of interest, such as elements. Control points (CP) were arranged in an equally spaced 5×5 grid and assigned LP values by a gradient based optimizer. A similar approach to Wu et al [9] was employed in this method. CP were positioned on the pre-twisted plate geometry at equal intervals of nodes. This ensured that each set of four adjacent CP control the same area over the geometry. CP were grouped into 10 chord-wise groups as shown in figure 1, to restrict the laminate to a span-wise only variation in stiffness. Grouping CP across the chord of the plate ensured that the stiffness did not vary across the chord of the plate. Although a combined span-wise and chord-wise variation in stiffness does provide an increase in performance over a span-wise variation alone, it is not used in this investigation as the extraction of the VAT laminate become more time consuming. This method of LP variation is suitable for more complex doubly curved surfaces. The *fit* function with spline surface interpolation within MATLAB was used to interpolate the LP values over the plate as shown in figure 2.

Figure 1: Control points for spline surface interpolation of lamination parameter values over a pre-twisted plate. Control point grouping and number shown.

5. OPTIMAL LAMINATION PARAMETER VARIATION

The gradient-based optimiser *fmincon* within *MATLAB* was used to determine the optimal LP values at the control points, with equation 5 used as a constraint assessed for all elements. The optimiser used the sum of the magnitude of the displacement of all nodes in the pre-twisted plate in equation 1 as the objective function to minimise. The optimal variation of control point LP values can be seen in figure 3

Figure 2: Spline surface interpolation over control points shown in figure 1.

and table 2. The optimal LP values indicate the plate requires high span-wise stiffness at the root i.e. 0° fibre angles for the first 6 control points due to the high centrifugal loading and bending moments in this region. From CP 6-8 the LP values change to provide an increase in torsional stiffness i.e. $\cong \pm 45^\circ$ fibre angles at CP 8, to reduce the untwist that is observed along the span. At the tip, CP 9-10 have increased chord-wise stiffness to reduce chord-wise bending that occurs in this region. It was observed between control points 6 and 9 there is a large difference in LP values, thus indicating a VAT laminate would need a high rate of change of fibre angle to match the optimal lamination parameter values. Therefore, a method needed to be developed to limit the variation of LP in relation to what is manufacturable.

Figure 3: Optimal lamination parameter variation in ξ_1^A and ξ_2^A design space.

Control Point	Lamination Parameter Value	
	$\xi_1^{[A,D]}$	$\xi_2^{[A,D]}$
1	0.918	0.998
2	0.984	1.000
3	0.964	0.994
4	0.868	0.962
5	0.888	0.843
6	0.869	0.906
7	0.500	0.228
8	0.064	-0.661
9	-0.646	0.516
10	-0.670	0.168

Table 2: Optimal control point lamination parameter values

6. LIMITING LAMINATION PARAMETER VARIATION

The main limiting factor that determines the maximum stiffness variation of an AFP manufactured VAT laminate is the minimum steering radius or maximum rate of fibre angle change of an AFP machine [11], with typical minimum steering radii of 508-635mm seen in literature[12]. Therefore, the variation in LP needs to be restricted in relation to minimum AFP turning radii. Derivation of stacking sequence from LP cannot be explicitly derived, which makes it difficult to accurately define a realistic LP change. Considering the LP values of all balanced and symmetric 16 ply laminates of the stacking sequence $[\pm\theta_1/\pm\theta_2/\pm\theta_3/\pm\theta_4]_s$, where ply angles are multiples of 5° i.e. $\theta_i = [-90^\circ, -85^\circ, -80^\circ \dots 90^\circ]$, all possible values of ξ_1^A and ξ_2^A are shown in figure 4a. Considering the laminate $\xi_1^A = \xi_2^A = 1$, which would require a stacking sequence of $[0^\circ_{16}]$, if a maximum change of fibre angle 60° , 45° and 30° was allowed, the laminates in which this maximum fibre angle change is not exceeded are shown in figure 4a. The feasible change in LP can then be taken as the convex hull of all the feasible laminates. The same can be seen for a starting point of $\xi_1^A = 0$ and $\xi_2^A = 0$ i.e. a $[(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_s]_s$ or QI laminate in figure 4b.

It is reasonable to approximate the maximum LP variation by approximating the stacking sequence of the CP LP and the design space created by laminates in which the maximum ply angle change has not been exceeded. A minimum turning radius of 643mm which is equal to a maximum rate of change of fibre angle of $140^\circ/\text{m}$ was used in this case. The CP were equally spaced along the plate, with the maximum allowable ply angle change between each combination of CP being their respective distance apart multiplied by the maximum rate of fibre angle change ($140^\circ/\text{m}$). The design space was approximated by taking the convex hull of the laminates with feasible fibre angle change using the *convhull MATLAB* function. The points of the convex hull were converted to a set of inequality constraints used by the gradient based optimiser using the *vert2con* function. This method was used as constraints between every combination of CP to ensure the variation of LP over the whole plate was realistic.

Optimal LP variation using this method of restraining the LP variation can be seen in figure 5 and table 3. The most notable difference between the unconstrained and constrained results can be seen between the reduction in variation between CP 7-10.

Figure 4: Feasible change in ξ_1^A and ξ_2^A for a 16 ply balanced and symmetric laminate of limited ply angle variation from an initial laminate start points.

Figure 5: Constrained optimal lamination parameter variation in ξ_1^A and ξ_2^A design space.

Control Point	Lamination Parameter Value	
	$\xi_1^{[A,D]}$	$\xi_2^{[A,D]}$
1	0.977	0.991
2	0.973	0.974
3	0.951	0.882
4	0.936	0.796
5	0.891	0.706
6	0.818	0.564
7	0.660	0.313
8	0.437	-0.155
9	0.074	-0.322
10	-0.246	-0.178

Table 3: Constrained optimal control point lamination parameter values

7. VARIABLE ANGLE TOW PATH ON DOUBLY CURVED SURFACE

To extract the VAT laminate that closely matches the optimal stiffness for a pre-twisted plate, a method in which to define fibre angle variation and therefore, local fibre angle for each ply over a doubly curved surface needed to be developed. As previously mentioned, VAT laminates have been used for structures that are flat or have curvature in a single direction, such as a cylinder. This becomes more complex for a doubly curved surface as the tows need to be spaced at the correct tow offset over the surface in order to tessellate sufficiently. In general, the tow paths are defined using a datum curve from which the adjacent tows are offset from to ensure they tessellate correctly. The method in which the adjacent tows are offset can be split into two categories, shifted and parallel. Even with the same reference curve, these two methods can produce very different tow path variation. The shifted method assumes that each additional tow has the same shape as the baseline case, but it is shifted in a direction perpendicular to the stiffness variation until the whole ply area is covered. The parallel method places the adjacent tows exactly parallel at a constant distance from the reference curve. Determining the paths of the offset tows using the parallel method can become difficult and complex for reference curves with more than one rate of fibre angle change as paths of infinite curvature can be produced. The shifted method is the simplest of the tow offset methods to use, although it can produce large thickness change due to tow gaps and/or overlaps for high fibre angle changes.

A *MATLAB* script was created to define a VAT ply onto a twisted plate, but it is also suitable for more complex doubly curved surfaces. The shifted method was used in this investigation due to its relative simplicity. Firstly a datum curve is projected onto the surface of the plate using a piece-wise Bézier curve notation developed by Kim et al [13], as shown by the blue curve in figure 6. The curve was defined using 6 variables with the notation $\phi < \alpha_0(\gamma_1)\alpha_1(\gamma_2)\alpha_2 >$, where α_i , γ_i and ϕ are junction point angles, angle variation coefficient and direction of fibre angle variation respectively. The datum curve is constructed from a number of discrete points, referred to here as seed points. For more detail on how these variables effect the curve see Kim et al [13].

To ensure tessellation of the tows, the correct offset for adjacent tows needs to be found. This was achieved by finding the point in the shifting direction in the xy plane from the datum curve seed points such that its arc length over the surface is equal to that of a multiple of a tow width. The arc length was calculated by discretising the arc using a large arbitrary number of points at small increments in the shifting direction and searching for the correct distance in the shifting direction in the xy plane until the

Figure 6: Variable angle tow ply on pre-twisted plate surface. Datum line shown in blue and subsequent adjacent tow offset lines shown in black. VAT ply is defined using variables $30^\circ < 30^\circ(0.25) - 30^\circ(0.75) 30^\circ >$.

arc length was equal to a multiple of a tow width. This was repeated for each seed point until there were enough adjacent tows of coordinates x_{Tij} , y_{Tij} and z_{Tij} to cover the whole surface, where i and j are datum curve seed point number and tow number respectively.

The local fibre angle on a doubly curved surface is subjective depending on what is chosen as its reference direction. This would usually be taken relative to a 0° ply, which, for a flat plate would lie in x direction. This is not necessarily true for a 0° ply on a doubly curved surface for the tows to correctly tessellate. Therefore, the angle difference between a VAT ply of interest and a 0° ply i.e. $0^\circ < 0^\circ(0.25) 0^\circ(0.75) 0^\circ >$, needs to be calculated to determine the local fibre angle. Firstly, the angle difference between the vectors for each point on the tows \vec{T}_{ij} relative to the vector in the x direction $\vec{T}_{x_{ij}}$ are calculated. The vector in the x direction for each point on a tow is given by

$$\overrightarrow{T_{x_{ij}}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ f_x(x_{Tij}, y_{Tij}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where $f_x = \partial f / \partial x$ is the partial derivative with respect to x . The vectors for every tow point $\overrightarrow{T_{ij}}$ are calculated using

$$\overrightarrow{T_{ij}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{T(i+1)j} - x_{Tij} \\ y_{T(i+1)j} - y_{Tij} \\ z_{T(i+1)j} - z_{Tij} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Using equations 7 and 8, the angle of the tow relative to the local x vector θ_{Tx} is calculated using

$$\theta_{Tx} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\overrightarrow{T_{x_{ij}}} \cdot \overrightarrow{T_{ij}}}{|\overrightarrow{T_{x_{ij}}}| \cdot |\overrightarrow{T_{ij}}|} \right) \quad (9)$$

The local fibre angle θ_{Ex} of each element centre relative to the vector in the x direction can then be calculated by interpolating x_{Tij} , y_{Tij} and θ_{Tx} for the position of the element centres. The local fibre element relative to a 0° ply can simply be calculated by subtracting the element fibre angle for a 0° ply from the VAT ply of interest.

8. VARIABLE ANGLE TOW STACKING SEQUENCE EXTRACTION

Once the optimal LP have been calculated, the stacking sequence that is the closest match to it needs to be found. Yamazaki [10] used a genetic algorithm (GA) for the minimisation of the geometric distances between the LP of the current stacking sequence using equation 3, and the optimal LP using

$$\text{Minimise} \quad f(\xi) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{12} (\xi_i - \xi_i^{opt})^2} \quad (10)$$

where i is the LP index. Similarly to Yamazaki, Diaconu and Sekine [14] used the sum of the square of the differences between the lamination parameters. Wu et al [9] extracted realistic smooth and continuous VAT layups from variable LP designs using a GA and a non-linear continuous variation of fibre angle orientations for a flat rectangular plate. The non-linear distribution of the fibre angles were constructed using Lagrangian polynomials to interpolate over the plate, with 9 variables needed to define the fibre variation of each ply. The objective function of the VAT plate was then expressed as the mean value of the least-square distance between the target lamination parameters evaluated at many points.

This investigation used a combination of the objective functions used by Wu et al [9] and Diaconu and Sekine [14], minimising the sum of the square of the difference between the target optimal LP and those of the local stacking sequence, summed for every element of the model

$$\text{Minimise} \quad f(\xi) = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\sum_{i=1}^{12} (\xi_i - \xi_i^{opt})^2 \right) \quad (11)$$

where j and m are the element number and total number of elements respectively. Fibre angles at each element centre of the VAT plies defined by the optimisers were found using the method described in section 7. The LP of each element were then found using the stacking sequence of the element fibre angles through the thickness of the laminate and equation 3.

A two-step optimisation process was used to find the VAT plies that best match the optimal LP variation. Firstly, a GA was used to find a suitable VAT laminate definition from a pre-determined set of VAT plies for the second stage gradient based optimiser to further refine. All combinations of VAT plies with the defining variables of $\phi = [-30^\circ, 0^\circ, 30^\circ]$, $\alpha_{[0,1,2]} = [-30^\circ:15^\circ:45^\circ]$ with the angle variation coefficients constant at $\gamma_1 = 0.25$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.75$ were used. Plies where $\alpha_0 = \alpha_1 = \alpha_2$ were removed as these are essentially UD plies and replaced with a set of plies where $\phi = [0^\circ:5^\circ:85^\circ]$ and $\alpha_0 = \alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 0^\circ$. These plies were then mirrored about the x axis by changing the sign of ϕ and $\alpha_{[0,1,2]}$ values

to ensure balanced pairs were available. This left the GA with 953 different plies to choose from, each with a corresponding integer value index used by the GA to select it. In the first stage the laminate used was symmetric with balanced ply pairing, therefore, 24 variables were needed to define the 96 ply laminate.

The second stage used the gradient-based optimiser *fmincon* in *MATLAB* to further refine every VAT ply in the laminate individually. Bounds of $-90^\circ \leq \phi \leq 90^\circ$, $-60^\circ \leq \alpha_{[0,1,2]} \leq 60^\circ$, $0.15 \leq \gamma_1 \leq 0.35$ and $0.65 \leq \gamma_2 \leq 0.85$ were used. Once the optimiser had converged, all the variables needed to define all tow paths for every individual VAT ply have then been obtained.

Figure 7: Variable angle tow paths for first half of the laminate shown on the left. First ten plies are shown on the right.

9. VAT LAMINATE RESULTS

The first stage GA converged to a VAT laminate definition with an objective function of 114.6. This equals a mean difference between the 8 LP ($\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^A$ and $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^D$ due to symmetry) that can have non-zero values and the optimal LP of 0.0525 per element. The second stage gradient-based optimiser further reduced the objective function to 11.7 which equates to a mean difference 0.0168 per element. A visual summary of all the tow paths of every VAT ply in the first half of the symmetric laminate can be seen in figure 7, with the first 10 plies magnified.

10. CONCLUSION

This paper has demonstrated a method to vary LP, and therefore, the stiffness over a doubly curved surface using spline surface interpolation. This interpolation method is also suitable to define a combined chord-wise and span-wise variation in LP, when the CP are not grouped into chord-wise groups. A method in which to limit the variation of LP by linking the realistic change to typical AFP machine minimum turning radii has also been discussed and demonstrated. By approximating the stacking sequence from a position in LP space, the maximum feasible change in LP can be approximated by taking the convex hull of LP values of laminates in which the maximum ply angle change has not been exceeded. This provides a link between the stiffness requirements and manufacture that is often missed when using variable LP for variable stiffness laminate optimisation. A method in which to define a VAT ply onto a doubly curved surface, whilst ensuring correct tow tessellation in concurrence with the shifting method, and then extract local fibre angle was discussed and demonstrated. A two-stage optimisation process was then used to define a VAT laminate that closely matches the AFP manufacturing constrained optimal LP to a reasonable difference.

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